

QUALIFIED TEACHER – EFFECTIVE LESSON ORGANIZER

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada malakali pedagoglarning darsni tashkil etishda o'ziga xos usul va texnologiyalardan foydalanishi o'qitish faoliyatining samaradorligiga ta'siri borasida so'z yuritiladi. Pedagog kadrlarning malakasini oshirish qonun hujjatlarida belgilab qo'yilganligi batafsil yoritib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagog, kadrlar, malaka oshirish, qayta tayyorlash, intellektual salohiyat, ta'lim tizimi, samarali dars.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается влияние использования квалифицированными педагогами специальных методов и технологий на эффективность педагогической деятельности. Подробно поясняется, что подготовка педагогических кадров определена законодательством.

Ключевые слова: педагог, кадры, повышение квалификации, переподготовка, интеллектуальный потенциал, система образования, эффективный урок.

Abstract: This article discusses the impact of the use of specific methods and technologies by qualified teachers in organizing lessons on the effectiveness of teaching activities. The fact that the professional development of teaching staff is stipulated in the legislation is explained in detail.

Keywords: teacher, personnel, professional development, retraining, intellectual potential, education system, effective lesson.

Today, the extensive reforms being implemented in the education system require a fundamental improvement of this system, the identification of targeted areas for the training of specialists with higher education, especially the continuous improvement of the professional qualifications and knowledge level of pedagogical personnel. Such changes require new innovative approaches to all spheres of social life, a review of existing views, concepts and relationships through the lens of progress and criteria of efficiency. The need for extensive reforms in the field of education is due to the fact that training potential personnel in accordance with world standards is of great importance for our independent Republic to find its place in the world community,

transition to a market economy, and not lag behind scientific and technical development. The reforms implemented and the adopted regulatory legal acts fully reveal the essence of the process of training competent teachers who are competent individuals, qualified specialists, and masters of their profession. The development of any state depends on its intellectual potential. Intellectual potential is a criterion for training independent-minded, qualified, educated, and highly qualified personnel capable of ensuring modern development in line with international standards. As our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich rightly noted, “Our youth must be independent-minded, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, and be able to mature and be happy, becoming people who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale,” it is no coincidence that special emphasis is placed on the fact that “another of the most important tasks of the education sector is undoubtedly to educate a new generation, educated young people who have mastered the basics of science and their specialty, which is necessary for today”.

Educating competent and educated youth is only possible for qualified teachers who work tirelessly on themselves, constantly develop themselves and further improve their knowledge. Such teachers use all their skills in educating the future generation, reveal their talents, and show dedication in educating and training the young generation to become mature personnel. The famous pedagogue-humanist of his time, Czech writer Jan Amon Komensky, highly appreciated the role of a teacher in developing a child's worldview, writing that teaching is "a very honorable profession that stands higher than any other profession on earth." One of the reforms in the field of education of our state is the adoption of advanced foreign experiences in improving the education system. During the implementation of these reforms, school textbooks are being repeatedly changed based on the National Curriculum. Effective teaching of these textbooks to students requires high skills and qualifications from the teacher. Therefore, teachers often go to advanced training institutions to work on themselves and improve their skills. At this point, I would like to touch on the term qualification, this concept is defined in Article 3 of the Law "On Education" called Basic Concepts and in this article it is defined as follows: "Qualification - the level of knowledge, abilities, skills and abilities of a person, which expresses his readiness to perform a certain type of professional activity, confirmed by an appropriate document on education".

The development of pedagogical staff is also stipulated in the legislative documents of our state. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4732 dated June 12, 2015 “On measures to further improve the

system of retraining and advanced training of managerial and pedagogical staff of higher educational institutions” and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 242 dated August 20, 2015 “On measures to organize retraining and advanced training of managerial and pedagogical staff of higher educational institutions”, the activities of the educational institutions have been improved in order to radically improve the quality of training highly qualified specialists and introduce an improved system of regular retraining in accordance with modern requirements. The purpose of the network center is to improve the quality of the processes of retraining and advanced training of teaching staff of higher educational institutions, to adapt their knowledge and professional skills to the rapid development of economic sectors in specific areas (specialties), to introduce innovations in the industry into the educational process, and to assist professors and teachers in mastering new techniques and technologies in relevant areas. Article 44 of the Law "On Education", approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 23, 2020, is on the right to engage in pedagogical activity, and this article establishes that a teacher must have completed advanced training and retraining courses. Article 10 of the Law "On the Status of a Teacher", adopted on February 1, 2024, is on retraining and advanced training of teachers. Accordingly: Retraining of teachers is carried out in order to provide them with additional professional knowledge, qualifications and skills and to provide them with the opportunity to carry out labor activities in accordance with their basic specialty and profession.

In essence, the advanced training of teachers is carried out in order to provide them with opportunities to deepen and update their professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, as well as to increase their category (position). This activity is carried out in special educational organizations within the period and in the form established by state educational requirements.

During the retraining and advanced training process, a teacher may voluntarily master additional subjects (foreign language, information technologies, social and humanitarian subjects, etc.) in addition to his professional subjects. When the curriculum and curriculum change (when a new subject is introduced or an existing subject is excluded), teachers of state educational organizations may be retrained in a new related subject. Advanced training of teachers of non-state educational organizations is carried out in accordance with the procedure established by the employer.

There are 2 forms of professional development for teaching staff:

1. direct (training according to educational programs)
2. indirect (training without educational programs)

Advanced training of teaching staff is carried out in the following forms:

- with dismissal from the main job;
- with partial dismissal from the main job (adapted method);
- without dismissal from the main job (distance learning).

Advanced training with dismissal from the main job and with partial dismissal from the main job (in a coordinated manner) is carried out on the basis of the regional center.

50 or 25 percent of the total duration of the advanced training course with partial dismissal from the main job (in a coordinated manner) is allocated to classroom training at the regional center. The rest of the course involves practical training. Practical training is allowed to be carried out at the main place of work.

Control is provided for each mastered module of practical training in the form of tests, abstract submission, practice report, etc.

The distance learning form of training without dismissal from the main job is used.

The duration of advanced training of pedagogical staff is determined depending on the forms of its organization and the requirements set by the customer, taking into account the level of professional qualifications of the pedagogical employee and individual professional needs.

Teachers are required to undergo advanced training at least once every 5 years.

The maximum volume of classroom training and independent work for direct forms of advanced training is set at 36 hours per week.

So what achievements can a teacher achieve if he is qualified?

As is known, during advanced training, teachers learn to work with various new and innovative ideas and projects, master modern methods and technologies, and learn new knowledge. They exchange experience with many teachers similar to themselves and introduce innovations into their teaching activities. These methods give effective results in working with students and organizing lessons. When working with students, such teachers increase their interest in science and encourage them to acquire knowledge effectively. When organizing lesson processes in an interesting, unusual, and creative way, teachers develop students in a new and innovative way, based on their interests. For students, lessons that are always organized in the same system seem boring, and this can extinguish their interest in science. However, a qualified teacher knows very well how to teach children, how to work with them. This is why in the competition of teachers, the best always win.

In conclusion, based on the above considerations, it can be said that in order to achieve efficiency in the education system, first of all, it is required that pedagogical personnel be qualified, skilled, capable and have pedagogical tact, as well as deep knowledge and skills in their specialty. After all, since the upbringing of the younger generation is the main and main task of the teacher, such an honorable profession requiring such responsibility can only be entrusted to mature specialists in their profession. A teacher, participating in the process of educating a harmonious generation, should not only be an example to those around him with his spiritual and moral culture, but also be able to demonstrate his pedagogical skills, and as a mature teacher, consider it his professional duty to make a worthy contribution to the work of training qualified personnel.

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